

**PASSAGE-SPECTRAL METHOD FOR TURBOMACHINERY LONG WAVE-LENGTH
FLOW INSTABILITIES**

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ABSTRACT

Numerical simulations of non-axisymmetric and unsteady flows are normally conducted using full-annulus geometries and U-RANS solvers. In general, nonlinear flow disturbances in time and/or space can be identified and represented by a discrete Fourier series as long as they are periodic. Single passage methods cannot capture this unsteady circumferential non-uniformities when the frequency is unknown. The identification and characterization of mechanisms related to flow instabilities with a reduction in computational resources should improve prediction methods and lead to more efficient control strategies, preserving the accuracy of a full domain solution. The proposed method presents for the first time an efficient means of approximating flows with spatial Fourier methods, extending the modeling to 3-D non-axisymmetrical unsteady flows without any assumed frequency in order to capture the long length-scale unsteady flow features of interest with a drastic reduction in number of reduced-passages to be required. Flow variables at the periodic boundaries are then continuously updated from the spatial Fourier coefficients of the uniformly spaced reduced-passage domains with the corresponding phase shift correction. An unsteady stall flow of a fan-stage at 50% (subsonic) of the design speed will be presented as a validation case to demonstrate effectiveness of the present method giving a comparison

between the solution obtained with low number of harmonics against full-annulus solution. The stall unsteadiness is deterministic by higher frequency fluctuations caused by perturbations with a length-scale of the order of a blade pitch and long-wave rotating structures with length-scale of the order of the circumference domain. The present method accurately reproduces the unsteadiness associated to the large scales present in modal stall in a fan-stage with even one harmonic, capturing the characteristic features of a complex flow due to the tip leakage vortex with a propagation speed of approximately 70% to 80% of rotor speed counter to the rotation.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of computer power and the advancements in numerical techniques have made Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) a powerful and essential tool for the design and analysis of turbomachinery flows. There have been considerable efforts devoted to the development of novel numerical methods which, making assumptions about the time/space periodicity of the flow, take advantage of it to reduce the computational cost required to obtain the desired solution. This problem is exacerbated when dealing with unsteady, multi-row configurations. Frequently, the flow is assumed to be periodic in time with a known fundamental frequency associated to the forcing of the flow. This is actually the case in forced response or uncoupled flutter problems where the fundamental frequencies are respectively, the blade-passing frequency and the natural frequency of

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the rotor blade. In this case the solution is expanded in a time Fourier series where, depending on the number of retained harmonics, linear [1] or non-linear harmonic [2, 3] methods are formulated. See the thorough review of He [4] or Dowell and Hall [5] for a more extensive discussion of the ranking of methods. However, when the unsteadiness of the flow is driven by flow instabilities, the fundamental frequency is not *a priori* known and need to be determined as a part of the solution. Still some methods have been attempted to expand the problem in a time Fourier series [6]. Turbomachinery flows are characterized by their spatial cyclic symmetry, and numerical methods taking advantage of it have been proposed to reduce their complexity and cost.

The use of spatial Fourier methods for computing nonlinear time-domain unsteady flows in turbomachinery was first proposed by He [7], who also applied the discrete spatial Fourier transformation into non-axisymmetric unsteady flows in axisymmetric rotor disc cavities [8]. More recently, time-domain Fourier methods have been used for general non-axisymmetric flows across multiple blade rows by Stapelfeldt et al. [9], who extended the method exploiting the time/space periodicity where distortions and interactions in the same frame of reference give rise to stationary passage-passage circumferential perturbations.

The present work is aimed at extending and applying the spatial Fourier modeling to 3-D non-axisymmetric unsteady flows subject to capture the long wave-length flow instabilities without any implicit assumption about the temporal periodicity of the flow. This approach gives the user control over the number of spatial harmonics needed flow length scales spanning over several blade passages, significantly reducing the computational resources, removing higher harmonics that may not be of interest. This kind of methodology is applicable to the simulation of the onset of compressor instabilities (rotating stall) and the long wave-length instabilities which can be seen in the drum and under-platform cavities of turbines and compressors. The main uncertainty in applying these methods to trigger flow instabilities is to determine if the reduced number of harmonics in the simulation can preclude the excitation of the instability.

The methodology and flow solver are validated on a stalled fan-stage at 50% (subsonic) of the design speed, predicting the existence of long-scale waves that have been previously reported in some experiments [10, 11]. Rotating stall or surge behaviour are defined by a complete breakdown of steady flow through the whole compressor, resulting in large fluctuations of flow with respect to time, and subsequent aeromechanical damage to the stage. Avoiding stall inception in operation conditions is one of the most important issues for a fan designer. From the performance point of view, it is desirable to operate them at the highest possible pressure ratios and efficiency but such operating conditions are inherently unstable due to aerodynamic instability phenomena. The complex nature of unsteady flows in a fan-stage presents a computational and numerical challenge as full-annulus simulations and long domains are required [12, 13]. Computa-

tionally efficient analysis tools for this kind of stall phenomenon when designing rotor blades are highly desirable. The formation of stall inception is a local instability in which the circumferential flow pattern is disturbed and reduced flow rate gives rise to flow separation, results in large fluctuations of flow with respect to time where one or more stall cells propagates at an unknown fraction of the rotor speed. The asymmetry of the flow causes non-uniform circumferential pressure distortions which can trigger a strong aeromechanical response in the fan blades. This kind of operating conditions at the fan is usually carried on by expensive unsteady full-annulus calculation due to the fact that numerical analysis considering only a part of annulus may not predict accurately the unsteady features of the long length scale disturbances flow like modal as well as the short length disturbances with high nonlinearities. The formation of long wave-length disturbances and a short wave-length inception on a fan-stage under rotating stall condition is analyzed using the Passage-Spectral Method solutions. It was observed that both could exist in the same compressor and could lead to a rotating stall [14, 15]. A short wave-length disturbance, once formed, can lead to rotating stall quickly usually within a few rotor revolutions with a velocity of a fraction of the rotor speed. This type of stall inception was first identified experimentally by Day [16], where a very small unstable disturbance grows to become a fully developed stall cell in few rotor revolutions. The basic assumption is that the length scales of disturbances are much larger than one blade pitch, with a length of the order of the rotor circumference. This phenomenon was previously investigated by some researchers as modal inception [17, 18]. It is then necessary to accurately predict the modal type inception at peak pressure rise condition [19], on the order of one rotor circumference with the initiation of rotating stall, which emerged due to tip clearance vortex breakdown [20]. In order to predict this stall flow behaviour only a few low-order harmonics should suffice. The validation presented in this work was accomplished by the comparison of the PSM solution with one and two harmonics with the full-annulus calculation analyzing the origin of the stall cells filtering the higher harmonics.

NOMENCLATURE

A_n, B_n	Fourier coefficient for order n harmonics
k	number of circumferential harmonics
N_b	number of rotor blades of the fan
P	pitch
p_0	inlet stagnation pressure
R	computation reduction factor
T	time period
T_{struct}	time period of the slow-rotating structures
\mathbf{U}	vector of conservation variables
$\hat{\mathbf{U}}$	n -th spatial harmonic of \mathbf{U} values
\mathbf{x}	cylindrical coordinate vector

Greek Symbols

ζ	local circumferential coordinate [rad]
θ	global circumferential coordinate [rad]
Ω	angular rotation speed [rpm]

Acronyms

<i>CFD</i>	Computational Fluid Dynamics
<i>U – RANS</i>	Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes
<i>PSM</i>	Passage-Spectral Method

NUMERICAL FORMULATION

Flow Solver

The purpose of using a Fourier modeling is to reduce the computing resource required by a direct calculation of the whole domain of 360° circumference as long as a spatial periodicity can be defined. The circumferential domain can be truncated to such an extent as long as it can provide sufficient information to carry out the Fourier transform. Assuming that circumferential non-uniformities are of large wave-length, a spatial Fourier spectrum in the time domain in non-axisymmetrical geometry configurations is proposed to simultaneously approximate the instantaneous circumferential distribution as previously done by He [7, 8] for axisymmetric geometries. Now we use a reduced-passage model as the minimum non-axisymmetric mesh to build the entire full 360° domain. The only input of the method is the number of harmonics, k , retained through the spatial reconstruction of the solution. The number of samples needed to build k harmonics on the azimuthal direction is $2k + 1$. The order of the method then only depends on the number of passages used in the computation. The sampling single-passage computational domains are uniformly spaced along the circumference, being the j -th domain located at:

$$\theta_j = \frac{j-1}{2k+1} 2\pi \quad (1)$$

Figure 1 shows an sketch of the single-passage domains required to solve 2 harmonics in the azimuthal direction. At any time instant t , the flow variable is decomposed so that the circumferential development and transportation of the large scale structures, which will in turn influence the flow losses and heat transfer, is approximated by a Fourier series of k harmonics. We would only need as many reduced-passage domains in the circumferential direction as those required to determine the number of harmonics retained in the Fourier model, $2k + 1$. The three-dimensional unsteady Navier-Stokes equations in conservative form for an arbitrary control volume for each reduced-passage sample mesh can be written in compact form

FIGURE 1. Reduced-passage domains for 2 harmonics.

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{\Gamma} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{U}_i^1 \\ \mathbf{U}_i^2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{U}_i^{2k+1} \end{pmatrix} d\Gamma + \int_{\Sigma} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{F}_i^1 \\ \mathbf{F}_i^2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{F}_i^{2k+1} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \mathbf{n} d\sigma = 0 \quad (2)$$

where U is the vector of conservative variables, F the sum of the inviscid and viscous fluxes, Γ the flow domain and $d\sigma$ the differential area pointing outward to the boundary. Passage-Spectral Method has been implemented into the in house code described by Burgos et al. [21], known as Mu^2s^2T . The code solves the 3D RANS equations using an edge-based data structure to spatially discretize the equations using a MUSCL scheme. Two-dimensional hybrid unstructured grids using an in-house grid generator (G2D) are generated to discretize the spatial domain and may contain cells with an arbitrary number of faces. The spatial discretization is formally second order accurate, and a matrixial form of the numerical dissipation terms is used recurring to the Roe's matrix. The solution vector is stored at the vertexes of the cells. The control volume associated to a node is formed by connecting the median dual of the cells that surround it, using an edge-based data structure. The preconditioned semi-discrete version of non-linear equations for each internal node i for each of the $2k + 1$ sample mesh can be written using a finite volume approach as,

$$P_{ji}^{-1} \frac{d}{dt} \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{U}_i^1 \\ \mathbf{U}_i^2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{U}_i^{2k+1} \end{pmatrix} \right\} \Gamma_i + \sum_{j=1}^{n_{edges}} \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{F}_{ij}^1 \\ \mathbf{F}_{ij}^2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{F}_{ij}^{2k+1} \end{pmatrix} \right\} \cdot \mathbf{n}_{ij} \sigma_{ij} - D_{ij} = S \left(\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{U}_i^1 \\ \mathbf{U}_i^2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{U}_i^{2k+1} \end{pmatrix} \right) \quad (3)$$

where Γ_i is the control volume, σ_{ij} is the area associated to the edge ij , n_{edges} is the number of edges that surround the node i , F_{ij} represents the inviscid and viscous fluxes through area σ_{ij} , D_{ij} are the artificial dissipation terms, P_j^{-1} is the block-Jacobi preconditioning matrix, S is the source term. The code is parallelized using MPI and executed in GPUs to reduce the turn around time [22].

FIGURE 2. Updating periodic dummy cells.

FIGURE 3. Full-annulus of Fan-Stage.

Methodology

The goal is to be able to run a certain number of reduced-passages models (few lower order Fourier harmonics k) of the circumferential domain in order to determine the number of harmonics retained in the spatial Fourier model required to capture the large scale structures with any assumed temporal periodicity. At any time instant t , the flow variable is decomposed in k order Fourier series in the time domain, thus at any given (x, r)

$$\mathbf{U}(\mathbf{x}, \theta, t) = \sum_{n=0}^k \hat{\mathbf{U}}_n(\mathbf{x}, t) e^{in\theta} \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_n(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the n -th spatial harmonic of \mathbf{U} . The zero spatial harmonic coefficient $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_0$ corresponds then with the circumferentially averaged value. Note that \mathbf{x} is the local coordinate system inside a reduced-passage, which can in turn be expressed as $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}(x, r, \zeta)$, where ζ is the local circumferential coordinate, while θ is the global circumferential coordinate. Both coordinate systems are related by:

$$\theta_j = \zeta + \frac{j-1}{2k+1} 2\pi \quad (5)$$

where j is the passage number. The Fourier coefficients $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_n(\mathbf{x}, t)$ are time-dependent and need to be evaluated at every time step to approximate the instantaneous solution using the spatial Fourier series by summation over $2k+1$ passages distributed uniformly over the circumferential domain (see Fig.1 for $k=2$)

$$\hat{\mathbf{U}}_n(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{1}{2k+1} \sum_{j=1}^{2k+1} \mathbf{U}_j(x, r, \theta_j, t) e^{-in\theta} \quad (6)$$

We only need to evaluate flow variable at the two neighbors rows of dummy cells to enable second-order difference calculations in order to correct the boundary conditions at the opposite periodic boundary. Fourier coefficients $\hat{\mathbf{U}}_n$ are now calculated for both periodic boundary neighbors nodes. Once Fourier coefficients have been calculated at each mesh cell, we need to evaluate/assign the flow variables at the dummy points to enable fluxes and differences calculations at each fractional Runge-Kutta. A dummy

mesh at the periodic boundaries “per-up” and “per-down” in Fig.2 is used in order to evaluate new flow variables with the corresponding phase-shift Fourier transformation of the nodes in the inner domain of the opposite boundary, where the solution is known. The azimuthal phase-shift is now equal to the pitch of the reduced-passage samples, P . This implementation would have a minimum influence on the flux calculation routine, we only need to modify how the flux calculation is corrected at the periodic patches. The inside mesh domain is not affected by any Fourier calculation.

VALIDATION

An unsteady stall flow of a fan-stage model is conducted as a validation case by comparing the Passage-Spectral Method solution against the full-annulus direct solution. The goal is to use a few single-passage samples to capture the large scale structures of interest. The solutions with different number of harmonics will indicate the error with respect the full-annulus solution.

Unsteady Stall Fan-Stage

Rotating stall is seen as a transient intermediate stage between spatially periodic flow and complete breakdown leading to engine surge, which can be associated with the initiation of several types of fluid dynamic instabilities. Because of its complex and transient nature, it is difficult to either understand or model the onset rotating stall by CFD methods. However, a lot of progress in the use of CFD-type techniques for the calculation of rotating stall has been made [18, 23, 24]. A time-marching Passage-Spectral method is proposed in order to improve the understanding of the rotating stall inception and its

FIGURE 4. Computational reduced-passage grid for method validation against full-annulus solution.

Number of rotor blades	20
Rotational speed [rpm]	3672
Mass-flow [kg/s]	54.25
Pressure ratio	1.1
Nominal tip-clearance [mm]	0.8
Rotor aspect ratio	2.33

TABLE 1. Fan rotor blade operating conditions at 50% of the design speed specifications near stall.

propagation mechanism, as well as to significantly reduce the computational resources. The aim of this section is to identify if the present novel method would be able to predict the unsteady features associated to the large scales present in modal stall together with short wave-length disturbances with high nonlinearities for a low-aspect-ratio fan just retaining a few spatial harmonics. Of particular interest is the effect of external circumferential disturbances corresponding to inlet stagnation pressure distortion [25]. If a flow is inherently unstable, the development of an instability can be triggered by small flow distortions of relevant patterns. A minor physical irregularity in the blade or the approaching flow can lead to separation in blades ahead and will propagate along the compressor blades in the direction of rotor rotation. This can destroy axial symmetry of rotating flow and consequently part of the annulus will contain stalled blades while the remainder contains unstalled blades. In the present case the effect of background disturbances introduced by a perturbation to the inlet stagnation pressure is used to initiate a rotating-stall inception. The perturbation is of sinusoidal form with first mode ($n = 1$) in the absolute frame of reference with a dimensionless amplitude of $\Delta\bar{p}_0 = 0.002$,

$$p_0 = \bar{p}_0[1 + \Delta\bar{p}_0 \sin(n\theta)] \quad (7)$$

a) PSM - $k = 1$ (3 reduced-passages)

b) Full-Annulus direct solution

FIGURE 5. Snapshot of the relative Mach number at the mid-chord of the fan rotor during stall inception after 2 rotor revolutions.

This first mode perturbation, with its wave-length being equal to the circumference, was intended to be sufficiently large to initiate a rotating-stall inception but still small enough to be comparable to typical irregularities in a real fan-stage situation under inlet distortion.

The fan-stage validation case consists on 20 blade passages. The full-annulus computation sketch is shown in Fig.3. Taking into account rotating stall conditions and a modal disturbance with a wave-length of one circumference, it is desirable to locate the boundary of the computational domain far enough from the rotor blade as well as a mesh fine enough to resolve tip leakage flow. A steady single-passage subsonic solution at 50% of the design speed with uniform inlet stagnation pressure in a near-stall operating conditions, summarized in Tab.1, is used as the initial solution with periodic boundary conditions. Figure 4 sketches the single rotor blade mesh, which will be used in the PSM solu-

FIGURE 6. Entropy distribution of tip region (99% span from hub).

tion as the reduced-passage model to carry out the spatial Fourier transformation. Comparison of both full-annulus and PSM unsteady solutions were run with 2000 time steps per rotor revolution (20 blade passing periods) in order to resolve the transient during the spike onset. The number of pseudo time steps per physical time step was fixed to 60, which is large enough to achieve the convergence criteria. At outlet, the radial equilibrium equation was applied to the unsteady simulations to redistribute the near stall outlet static pressure at each time step. The static pressure at the outlet was increased in order to simulate the process approaching stall along a constant rotor-speed line on the fan performance map. The standard $k - \omega$ turbulence model with wall function is used.

Figure 5 displays a snapshot of the relative axial Mach number at the mid-chord of the rotor blade after two rotor revolutions for the full annulus solution and the one obtained with a single spatial harmonic (3 reduced passages). The creation of stall cells at the rotor tip can be clearly distinguished. After two rotor revolutions, it can be seen a sinusoidal type disturbance with a wave-length of one circumference. These perturbations with respect the base flow are localized in the rotor blade tip region and develop directly into stall cells. The first harmonic gradually increases across the whole domain for both solutions. Stall propagates from one side to its opposite, where the blade passages stay unstalled, in counter-rotation. The PSM solution with a single harmonic seems to be enough to capture the unsteadiness of the stall process. It is shown that a long wave pattern of a length-scale of the circumference together with short wave-length disturbances of the order of the pitch are triggered by the first mode perturbation.

Figure 6 compares the entropy distribution of several instantaneous solutions between the PSM and the full-annulus computations. The entropy contours are a good indication of separated vortical structures, because of the convective nature of entropy. The corresponding entropy contours for the PSM solutions with 1 harmonic (Fig.6a and Fig.6d) and 2 harmonics (Fig.6b and Fig.6e) are shown respectively for two different times. Figures 6c and 6f show the corresponding full-annulus solutions at the same two time instants in order to compare both the PSM and the full-annulus solutions. At 1 rotor revolution a spillage of tip leakage flow near the tip region (99% span from hub) occurs around the leading edge, as previously outlined by other authors for subsonic rotor speed [18]. The trajectory of the incoming flow with low entropy and tip clearance flows results in a balance on the interface plane obtaining a region with high entropy gradient on the leading edge. The result is a movement of the interface region toward the rotor leading edge plane in a counter rotating direction. In Fig.6 at 2 rotor revolutions, the first spillage changes the load distribution of the trailing edge and caused the propagation of the spillage along the blade row, increasing the amplitude of the first circumferential mode, resulting in a short-length scale multiple-cell pattern. The results show also that the incoming/tip clearance flow interface is aligned with the rotor leading edge plane at the blade tip. Both calculated flow field solutions from the two PSM solutions are in good agreement with that from the full-annulus solution (Fig.6c and Fig.6f) for both proposed instant times, respectively. The method is able to capture the non-axisymmetric behaviour with even one harmonic, indicating that the solutions are no longer harmonic-dependent, with the given number of harmonics.

FIGURE 7. Time history of the first 2 harmonics coefficients of the axial velocity component at a monitoring point near the outer casing at 1.25 axial chords upstream of fan.

The method accurately reproduced the full-annulus solution using only three passages, capturing the characteristic features of a complex flow due to the lip leakage vortex and shock wave interaction in response to a small passing perturbation of a pressure wave at the inlet, dividing into two clearly defined sector of stalled and unstalled flow. It can be shown that the low momentum flow in the tip region leads to damaging instability, developing a long wave pattern in the axial velocity, as shown in Fig.5. It can be concluded that the first mode perturbation p_0 has the most destabilizing effect. The tip leakage vortex shows a first circumferential mode periodic behaviour as the rotor enters and exits the distorted region at the near stall point. The phenomena described occur in the tip region, as shown in Fig.5 and Fig.6, where short wave-length spike disturbances have been experimentally detected.

We now focus on the harmonics behaviour during the transient development of the stall inception and the relevance of each harmonics into the transformed solution. Figure 7 shows the temporal signal of the first two spatial Fourier harmonics monitored on a tracking point at the rotor frame of reference on the casing at 1.25 axial chord upstream of the fan. For the first 1.5 rotor revolutions in Fig.7 small pulses with short length scales exist in the flow. The spillage of tip leakage flow at 1 rotor revolution around the leading edge, previously shown in Fig.6, causes a small asymmetric disturbance and appears as a small tick in the axial velocity time histories on the casing upstream of fan (see Fig.7). At approximately 1.5 rotor revolutions, the first harmonic of the PSM solution produce a sharp increase in

its amplitude, which indicates a rapid development of the non-axisymmetric flow near the monitoring point of this stall region. A small asymmetric disturbances is firstly created after 1.5 revolution and propagates along the fan blade row, creating a first circumferential harmonic, as shown in Fig.5 at 2 rotor revolutions. The amplitude of the first mode ($n = 1$) is about 10 times higher than that of the second mode ($n = 2$). The first harmonic is clearly identified as the most destabilizing effect (see Fig.7), resulting in a single-cell tip leakage vortex pattern rotating in the absolute frame. Having into account the conclusions previously outlined with the comparison of the entropy distribution with two PSM solutions with one and two harmonics, we can conclude that a single harmonic suffices in this case to accurately predict the whole domain behaviour of the full-annulus solution, indicating that the stall inception process is no longer harmonic-dependent. Once the process is triggered, the one circumferential mode pattern is shown to be persistent with time. The number of disturbances within the flow coincides with the mode order of the small inlet distortion. The present results might be interpreted as implying that first-order modal wave is the most unstable, and should be analyzed the stability of the solution when higher harmonics are excited. It could also be proven that as the mass flow is reduced, the intensity of flow disturbances, in terms of amplitude of the modes, increases.

The stall cell speed can be predicted from the monitoring of the axial velocity harmonics results shown in Fig.7. The passing velocity from one blade to another can be obtained using the difference between the velocity maxima (~ 0.2 rotor revolutions, see Fig.7). Knowing that each peak in Fig.7 is associated to the 20 blades of the fan-stage, and the time for one rotor revolution, the time period T_{struct} of the one mode perturbation is about 4 engine revolutions. Knowing that the relative angular velocity ratio of the structure in the rotor frame of reference can be evaluated with Eq.8

$$\frac{\Omega_{struct}}{\Omega} = 1 - \frac{T}{T_{struct}} \quad (8)$$

It is shown then that these disturbances in the rotor tip region rotate at around 75% of rotor speed counter to the rotation (see Eq.8). According to the results outlined by He [25], the shorter the stall cell scale, the higher the rotating speed. In the results obtained in this work, the length scale of the multiple-cell rotating stall perturbation is of the order of the pitch of the rotor blade, whereas the long-scale single-cell pattern could not be generated even with the first mode perturbation at the inlet. It is also suggested that to allow the long-scale first circumferential unstable mode to grow, the inlet/outlet length needs to be at least that similar to the circumference. The rotating speed of the short-scale rotating-stall pattern in the PSM solutions has a good agreement to the ones obtained with the full-annulus domain, and the fluctuations amplitude is also comparable. The method is then able to capture these rotating disturbances with an unknown frequency in the time-domain, obtaining the same stall cell prop-

FIGURE 8. Relative Mach number field of the PSM solution with $k = 1$ at 95% span from hub after two rotor revolutions.

agation speed as in the full-annulus solution. However, further investigation is desirable in order to identify if it is possible to predict the rotating stall when the transition from one cell to two or more takes place.

Once the method has been validated, we can analyze deeper the solutions obtained with 1 harmonic, which represents accurately the behaviour of the whole annulus domain. Figure 8 presents the stall inception structures downward in the span-wise direction inside the blade passage and the effect of stall inception upstream of fan. Figure 8 shows instantaneous Mach number at 95% span from hub at two rotor revolutions during the transient evolution of a half of the whole crown domain. Fluid originating from the tip clearance of one blade moves from an adjacent passage counter of the rotation. It is seen from the isolines contour that the trajectory of this fluid is such that there is impingement on the pressure side, resulting in a tip clearance backflow. It is illustrated the connection between the impingement and the generation of higher blockage. Tip leading edge vortex breaks down during stall inception while it develops without breakdown in the normal passages, with no connection of impingement between neighboring blades. The local pressure gradient is increased on the pressure surface at the rear of the blade passage in the region of the stalled blades in Fig.8, resulting in a non-axisymmetric pattern in the circumferential direction. Tip leakage flow suchlike impingement increases the strength of tip core vortex by propagating the wave in every direction. This phenomenon can be understood based on the downstream isolines of the Mach number results which show shifted lines in the incoming flow near the rotor leading edge. Another criteria can be outlined from the Fig.8, where the trailing edge backflow spillage for the stalled passages leaks through adjacent blades, building a

	$k = 1$	Full annulus
Number of points	$6M$	$40M$
Number of GPUs	2	8
Wall clock time per revolution (h)	12	20

TABLE 2. Computational comparison.

connection between passages down to rotor span.

We can conclude that Passage-Spectral method is able to predict the modal stall inception behaviour with a significant reduction in computation resources. The method accurately predict the non-uniformities of the flow and the modal stall behaviour without using an expensive full-annulus domain, however it is important to note that the uncertainty surrounding the stalling behaviour. With respect to the saving in computational resources, the reduction in circumferential mesh reduced-passage for an k order Fourier model in comparison with direct solution is given by

$$R = \frac{N_b}{2k + 1} \quad (9)$$

where N_b is the number of rotor blades of the fan. The reduction factor R in computational 3D non-axisymmetric domains in the circumferential direction for the direct whole annulus solution against PSM with 1 harmonic will be then $R = 20/3 \simeq 7$ (see Eq.9). Table 2 compares the computational effort requires for the two solutions.

CONCLUSIONS

A novel method for the resolution of the Navier-Stokes equation is presented using fast Fourier transforms in the time-domain with the aim to significantly reduce computational work for low unknown frequency analysis, filtering the unwanted higher harmonics and facilitating efficient computational predictions of the non-axisymmetric and unsteady flows. To the author's knowledge, this work presents for the first time the application of a reduced-passage method in the time domain to non-axisymmetric geometries such as rotating modal stall in a fan-stage. The modal type inception on the order of one rotor circumference in response to a small passing distortion of a static pressure first mode perturbation at the inlet has been identified with the initiation of stall inception with a short-length scale multiple-cell pattern, which emerged due to tip clearance vortex breakdown, using few low order harmonics solution in the circumferential direction. It is found a self-induced rotating propagation speed of the perturbation of 75% of rotor speed due to the modal stall process. We can conclude that the present method is able to fully capture nonlinearities into the whole crown, solving an unsteady time-domain non-axisymmetric solution without any assumed frequency. The PSM solutions indicate that a number of harmonics higher enough to capture non-axisymmetries resolved the unsteadiness of this kind of stall flows with adequate accuracy and a significant reduce in the computational time and memory. However, the solution with even one harmonic is shown to be able to qualitatively capture the non-axisymmetric behaviour. Frequency domain and single passage methods are typically limited to assumed periodically unsteady perturbations and ignore potentially important unknown variations in the underlying unsteady flow field. A reasonable agreement between direct and new Passage-Spectral Method solutions is achieved. The method accurately predicts the unsteady features associated to the large scales present in modal stall together with short wave-length disturbances with high nonlinearities for a low-aspect-ratio fan just retaining a few spatial harmonics.

The method presented here provides an efficient means of approximating flows with spatial Fourier methods, trying to facilitate the efficient analysis for design and optimization of the non-axisymmetric flow. It could be easily implemented in a standard time-domain CFD solver with a minimum influence on the flux calculation routine. It can contribute to a better understanding of the physics behind discrete flow disturbances represented by spatial harmonics. Generalized circumferential Fourier transform for non-axisymmetric complex geometries, such as the PSM described in this work, can be used to different applications with temporal and spatial length-scale disparities such as instabilities in cavities, rim-seal ingestion, inlet distortion, rotating stall, crosswind, etc. However, the studies performed have not still been validated and a wider range of applications must be analyzed in the future to build a complete understanding and adequate accuracy of the method.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Hall, K. C. and Lorence, C. B., "Calculation of three-dimensional unsteady flows in turbomachinery using the linearized harmonic Euler equations," *ASME 1992 International Gas Turbine and Aeroengine Congress and Exposition*, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 1992, pp. V005T14A013–V005T14A013.
- [2] He, L. and Ning, W., "Efficient approach for analysis of unsteady viscous flows in turbomachines," *AIAA journal*, Vol. 36, No. 11, 1998, pp. 2005–2012.
- [3] Hall, K. C., Thomas, J. P., and Clark, W. S., "Computation of unsteady nonlinear flows in cascades using a harmonic balance technique," *AIAA journal*, Vol. 40, No. 5, 2002, pp. 879–886.
- [4] He, L., "Fourier methods for turbomachinery applications," *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, Vol. 46, No. 8, 2010, pp. 329–341.
- [5] Dowell, E. H. and Hall, K. C., "Modeling of fluid-structure interaction," *Annual review of fluid mechanics*, Vol. 33, No. 1, 2001, pp. 445–490.
- [6] Van Der Weide, E., Gopinath, A., and Jameson, A., "Turbomachinery applications with the time spectral method," *35th AIAA Fluid Dynamics Conference and Exhibit*, 2005, p. 4905.
- [7] He, L., "Fourier modeling of steady and unsteady non-axisymmetrical flows," *Journal of propulsion and power*, Vol. 22, No. 1, 2006, pp. 197–201.
- [8] He, L., "Efficient computational model for nonaxisymmetric flow and heat transfer in rotating cavity," *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 133, No. 2, 2011, pp. 021018.
- [9] Stapelfeldt, S. C. and Di Mare, L., "Reduced passage method for multirow forced response computations," *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 53, No. 10, 2015, pp. 3049–3062.
- [10] Tryfonidis, M., Etchevers, O., Paduano, J., Epstein, A., and Hendricks, G., "Pre-stall behavior of several high-speed compressors," *ASME 1994 International Gas Turbine and Aeroengine Congress and Exposition*, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 1994, pp. V001T01A135–V001T01A135.
- [11] Day, I., Breuer, T., Escuret, J., Cherrett, M., and Wilson, A., "Stall inception and the prospects for active control in

- four high-speed compressors,” *Journal of turbomachinery*, Vol. 121, No. 1, 1999, pp. 18–27.
- [12] Im, H.-S., Chen, X., and Zha, G.-C., “Detached eddy simulation of unsteady stall flows of a full annulus transonic rotor,” *ASME Turbo Expo 2010: Power for Land, Sea, and Air*, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 2010, pp. 2627–2642.
- [13] Lee, K.-B., Wilson, M., and Vahdati, M., “Numerical Study on Aeroelastic Instability for a Low-Speed Fan,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 139, No. 7, 2017, pp. 071004.
- [14] Day, I. and Cumpsty, N., “The measurement and interpretation of flow within rotating stall cells in axial compressors,” *Journal of Mechanical Engineering Science*, Vol. 20, No. 2, 1978, pp. 101–114.
- [15] Greitzer, E., “Axial compressor stall phenomena,” *Journal of Fluids Engineering*, Vol. 102, No. 2, 1980, pp. 134–151.
- [16] Day, I., “Active suppression of rotating stall and surge in axial compressors,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 115, No. 1, 1993, pp. 40–47.
- [17] Tan, C., Day, I., Morris, S., and Wadia, A., “Spike-type compressor stall inception, detection, and control,” *Annual review of fluid mechanics*, Vol. 42, 2010, pp. 275–300.
- [18] Choi, M., Smith, N. H., and Vahdati, M., “Validation of numerical simulation for rotating stall in a transonic fan,” *Journal of turbomachinery*, Vol. 135, No. 2, 2013, pp. 021004.
- [19] Camp, T. and Day, I., “A Study of Spike and Modal Stall Inception Indication in Axial Compressor,” *ASME Paper, 97-GT-526*, 1997.
- [20] Chen, J.-P., Hathaway, M. D., and Herrick, G. P., “Pre-stall behavior of a transonic axial compressor stage via time-accurate numerical simulation,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 130, No. 4, 2008, pp. 041014.
- [21] Burgos, M. A., Contreras, J., and Corral, R., “Efficient edge-based rotor/stator interaction method,” *AIAA journal*, Vol. 49, No. 1, 2011, pp. 19–31.
- [22] Gisbert, F., Corral, R., and Pastor, G., “Implementation of an edge-based navier-stokes solver for unstructured grids in graphics processing units,” *ASME Paper No. GT2011-46224*, 2011.
- [23] Dodds, J. and Vahdati, M., “Rotating Stall Observations in a High Speed Compressor-Part II: Numerical Study,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 137, No. 5, 2015, pp. 051003.
- [24] Carnevale, M., Wang, F., Parry, A. B., Green, J. S., and di Mare, L., “Fan Similarity Model for the Fan-Intake Interaction Problem,” *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, Vol. 140, No. 5, 2018, pp. 051202.
- [25] He, L., “Computational study of rotating-stall inception in axial compressors,” *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, Vol. 13, No. 1, 1997, pp. 31–38.